

Kirttirāja and Kakanamaṭha Temple of Suhāniyā

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Kirttirāja was the fourth ruler of Kacchapaghāta dynasty of Gwalior, as recorded in the Sās-bahū temple inscription of Mahipāla dated VS 1150 (CE 1093). The dynasty came to prominence in the tenth century, after they were able to capture the fortress of Gwalior after the Gurjara Pratihāras. The Sās-bahū temple inscription describes that Vajradāmana 'put down the rising power of the ruler of Gādhinagara (Kanauj) and his proclamation drum... resounded on the fort of Gopādri'¹. The Kacchapaghātas of Suhāniyā (ancient Sirhnapāniya) subsequently ruled from the centre of Gwalior (ancient Gopādri, Gopagiri). Other branches of the family had their seats at Dūbkuṇḍ (ancient Caḍobh or Ḍobha) and Narwar (ancient Nalapura). Each branch secured distinctive geographical area. Of them, the most powerful branch was Gwalior, who seemed to have ruled the large tract bounded on the north and west by the river Cambal and undoubtedly the most important in terms of architectural activity.

The main source for the history of the Kacchapaghāta lineage of Suhāniyā and Gwalior is the stone slab inscription of Mahipāla inside the Sās temple situated on the Gwalior fort. The first historical person mentioned in the Sās-bahū inscription was Lakṣmaṇa, who is described in it as 'an ornament of the Kacchapaghāta race, who had, by force, extirpated mighty princes'². He was followed by Vajradāmana designated *mahārājādhirāja* in a Jaina image inscription discovered at Suhāniyā, dated VS 1034 (CE 977)³, who is known in the Sās-bahū inscription to have wrested by force the fort of Gopādri from the hands of some valiant ruler, possibly the Pratihāra monarch Vijayapāla, of Gādhinagara (Kanauj). Vajradāmana celebrated the victory by performing a *suvarṇa-tulādāna* and shifted the capital to Gwalior. He was succeeded by Maṅgalarāja, who is conventionally described as scattering his enemies as the Sun does the darkness. Maṅgalarāja was followed by Kirttirāja who defeated a mighty Mālava (Paramāra) army. His description in the inscription that 'in his march, the sheet of dust rising from the armies took away the colour of the sun and at the same time that of his enemies'⁴ does not appear to have been a boast for he is also said to have 'repulsed the army of the Mālava king, whose countless hosts met with defeat and received such a terrible shock that the multitudes of spears fallen from their hands in every direction through fear were later collected by the villagers and were used for fencing their houses'⁵.

The temple of Śiva, locally known by the name of Kakanamaṭha, is

most important of the monuments at Suhāniyā (26°35' N, 78°50' E) in District Morena of Madhya Pradesh. It is popularly believed to have been built by the orders of a queen named Kakanāvati or Kandanāvati from whom the temple derives its name⁶. But a verse in the Sanskrit inscription of the Sās-bahū temple on Gwalior fort confirms the authorship of this building, and records that in the town of Sirṁhapāniya Kirttirāja constructed a wonderful temple of the Lord of Pārvaṭī (i.e. Śiva), which shines like a column of glory:

*Adbhutaḥ Sirṁhapāniyanagare yena kāritaḥ /
kirttistambha ivābhāti prāsādaḥ Pārvaṭīpateḥ // 7*

Kakanamaṭha temple which is situated at a distance of about 2 km towards north of the village Suhāniyā, recorded to have been built by Kacchapaghāta ruler Kirttirāja, is a magnificent edifice even in its ruins and is astonishing in its sculptural wealth (Pl. XXI A). The temple facing east, built entirely of stone on a spacious platform, stands on a soaring ornate *pīṭha* and is encircled by at least four subsidiary shrines⁸. The temple proper consists of a sanctum enclosed by an ambulatory with three balconied transepts. In front of this are an *antarāla* (vestibule), a *gūḍhamaṇḍapa* (closed hall) with lateral transepts, and a *mukhamaṇḍapa* (porch) approached from the east by stairs. The steps were flanked by gigantic lions, like the temple at Paḍhāvalī, that have been removed to the Gujari Mahal Archaeological Museum, Gwalior and now stand on the either side of the entrance of the museum building. The *pīṭha* of the Kakanamaṭha temple is stylishly moulded, relieved by rows of rosettes, lotus blossoms in relief, a recessed band of triangular floral motifs interrupted by niched figures of deities, sliced open on the north side by a *praṇāli* (spouted channel) used to drain libations from the *liṅga* in the cella. The sanctum of the temple is of *pañcaratha* type. It has the usual *vedibandha* mouldings topped by a *jaṅghā* screening a row of large niched sculptures canopied by *torāṇas* and surmounted by a row of various friezes on the projections and with Vyālas and Surasundaris in the recesses. In the shrine is a Śiva *liṅga* still in worship. The sanctum doorway comprises of seven ornate *śākhās* (jambs) which include a large row of deities between two *mithuna-śākhās* (bands of couples). The *udumbara* (sill) bears elephants and recumbent lions, which is an exceptional example of sculpture and its linear style of the period to which it belongs. The *bhadrās* display larger projecting niches, which are now empty, and flanked by Surasundaris. The projections of the *karṇas* and the *pratirathas* have Dikpālas and Surasundaris. It is interesting to note that Aṣṭa Dikpālas, Indra, Agni, Yama, Nirṛti, Varuṇa, Vāyu, Kubera and Īsāna are shown on all the appropriate *karṇas* of *jaṅghā*. On the transepts of the sanctum and the *gūḍhamaṇḍapa* the *kaḥśāsana* balustrade is noteworthy. Though outer walls, balconies and facing stone of the spire have all fallen away, the spire

itself remains standing in its full height (around 37 m.). Only the rough masonry core and part of the *āmlasāraka* (serrated crown) have survived. The *maṇḍapa* soared to a height of three storeys and was crowned by a *ghanṭā* (bell-finial). The central ceiling is missing, while existing peripheral ceiling shows usual designs of cusped coffers. The *maṇḍapa* is supported by forty-two pillars. The *antarāla* has a single slanting row of four pillars while the *gūḍhamaṇḍapa* has four groups, each of four pillars, arranged in four rows in alignment with those of the *antarāla*. All the pillars are of the *bhadraka* style. They are very massive and tall and ornamented only on the upper part with bands of scrolls, *kirttimukha* and *ghaṭapallava*, and crowned by brackets of plain curved profile.

The *adhiṣṭhāna* and *jaṅghā* portion of the Kakanamaṭha temple bear the sculptures of deities, Dikpāla, Vyāla, Surasundarī, and a Gaṇa in the *pārśva maṇḍapikā*⁹. The marvellous beauty may be seen in the well carved characteristic features on the long and slim figures of the sculptures. The noteworthy sculptures of Suhāniyā are Yakṣa, Vāyu, Śiva seated on Nandi, Viṣṇu, Yama, Varāha, Agni, Indra, Brahmāṇi, Sūrya, Brahmā with Sāvitrī, four armed Pārvaṭī, Kamalāsānā, etc. Many single images of Suhāniyā have been taken to the Gujari Mahal Archaeological Museum of Gwalior, and Archaeological Survey Museum on Gwalior fort.

M. B. Garde had described an image of Viṣṇu Viśvarūpa from here. Another image of Viṣṇu Viśvarūpa is preserved in the Gujari Mahal Archaeological Museum of Gwalior. The most important and rare image is of Viṣṇu Viśvarūpa. This broken image has five heads of Viṣṇu - Saumya, Matsya, Kūrma, Varāha and Nṛsimha, and the remaining three hands out of six bear Paraśu, Hala, and bow-arrow¹⁰. Garde has referred to an image of Viṣṇu in the Viśvarūpa form possessing ten hands and five heads. In the background of this image are seen figures of Navagraha, Aśvamukhī Aṣṭa Vasu and other deities. Besides, Gaṇeśa, Cakra Puruṣa, Gadādevī and Anucara are seen carved on the image. According to Garde this image belonged to the early tenth century CE.¹¹

That the temple continues to exist even in the present position is only because of the preservation and conservation work that was undertaken from time to time. Recently Archaeological Survey of India repaired the *jagatī* and has done some conservation work. Before that, during 1925-27 the temple was taken for repair by M. B. Garde, Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior State. The jungle, which grew on the temple and on the large mound on which the temple stands, was cleared and rooted out, and the main temple was freed from its own heavy debris by which it was shrouded. The steps of

the staircase were reset, cracked or damaged lintels, architraves and pilasters were strengthened, and some hazardously hanging stones were either taken down or positioned into a safe arrangement, while a few decorative sculptures which had moved out of their position were reset¹². Prior to this, such type of work was done in VS 1950 (CE 1893), which is also recorded in the inscriptions on a pillar of the temple. Two inscriptions of VS 1950, engraved on a pillar in the Kakanamaṭha temple (Pl. XXII), in Nāgarī characters and Sanskrit language, record the restoration of the Mahādeva temple by Durgāprasāda.

A. TEXT

1. Śrī Mahādeva Jī ko
2. jīṇa-uddhāra karo
3. Śrī Vyāsa Śrī Durgā Prasa (sā) -
4. da Jī nemiṭṭ Śrī
5. śrāvaṇā vadī 10
6. saṁvat 1950

B. TEXT

1. Śrī Durgāprasāda Vyāsena
2. jīṇoddhāra Śivasya
3. cakvepto Umeṣvaṁ ka
4. caṁdraśva jāyano vi-
5. kramasya vai śrāvaṇa-
6. syāsīte pakṣeda-
7. śamyāṁ caṁdravāsa-
8. re Śrī Śaṁkara prasā-
9. dārthaṁ sarvahāṇai saṁ-
10. va[t] 1950

Besides the renovation records, there are some pilgrim records on the pillars which suggest that people visited the place to pay their homage to the god. On a pillar in the Kakanamaṭha, 2 lines' inscription in Nāgarī characters and Sanskrit language is engraved (of the period of about the 11 century).¹⁴ It mentions '1. Śrī Paliyaṭa 2. purohitaṭa.' Another pilgrim record of VS 1497 (CE 1140) is engraved on a pillar in the Kakanamaṭha temple, in 9 lines in Nāgarī characters and local dialects. This pilgrim record mentions Sadyāṭa mukalu, son of Sādhuṇī. It belongs to the time of a Tomar ruler of Gwalior, Durhgara and refers the name of Dekhaṇa, son of Kaṁkala, who was a resident of Nalapura fort¹⁵.

TEXT

1. Arṁvikāpresāṇu āai-
2. vi sidhi Śrī saṁvat 1497
3. vaisaṣu 9 ravau Śrī Deṁ(Ḍuṁ)gara
4. nṛpaḥ Sādhuṇī putra Sa
5. dyāṭa mukalu Nala-
6. puragaḍha vāstavyā
7. Kaṁkala purū(tra) Deṣaṇa a-
8. ai //
9. thārū / kopālāganu

On a pillar in the Kakanamaṭha, an inscription of 6 lines is engraved in Nāgarī script and local dialect; mentions Kandupālikṣa and Śrīvi of Nalapura, in late character¹⁶.

TEXT

1. Aikuhakāruduvārakadvi-
2. chā Kānaudāmāta // Aihuka
3. vatiha nisigaha // sura-
4. ta samaija Kandupālikṣa
5. tanūrāvu Śrīvi Nala-
6. purasthiti

One of the pillars of the Kakanamaṭha temple bears an inscription of VS 1878 (CE 1821) which is written in 2 lines, in Nāgarī script and reads 1. Motorama saṁvat 187? 2. 1878¹⁷.

It is difficult to determine with certitude when Kirttirāja ascended the throne. On the basis of Sās-bahū temple inscription scholars have suggested numerous dates for Kirttirāja and Kakanamaṭha temple. H.C. Ray took this event as happening during CE 1015-1035¹⁸. This view is accepted by many other scholars. H.V. Trivedi¹⁹ assigns his reign to CE 1005-1030. Garde conjectured 1000 CE to be the appropriate date for his accession.²⁰ Cunningham believed his time in power about 990-1010 CE²¹. In the opinion of Patil the temple was freshly built in the 11th century CE²² and R. N. Misra²³ follows the same view. But these dates go against the date 'Om saṁvat / 1044 śudi 3' that is carved on the Kakanamaṭha temple and noticed by us for the first time (Pl. XXI B). This inscription specifies that the author of the temple, Kirttirāja was apparently on the throne in VS 1044 (CE 987) and possibly his accession was prior to this date because the inscription under discussion is engraved on the western *janḡhā* of the sanctum. This suggests that the construction work of the temple was started some time earlier and

reached at least up to the *janghā* level, if not completed till CE 987. In addition, on one of the stone lions (now standing on the other side of the entrance of Gujari Mahal Museum building) there is an inscription, the Nāgarī characters of which are considered by scholars to be about the 10th century.²⁴ It is not much clear, however, tentatively in the first line it records 'Sāduhalarugaheda ca raha' and in the second line 'airābhēṇapaladevata varaṇa'. The 10th century date of the stone lion also supports the view that the construction of temple was started prior to the 11th century CE.

If the date, CE 987 is accepted for the rule of Kirttirāja the early history of Kacchapaghāta requires a few revisions. The Sās-bahū temple inscription informs us that 'Vajradāmana, son of Lakṣmaṇa, by his irresistible strong arms captured the fort of Gwalior from the ruler of Gādhinagara (Kanauj)'. His inscription of VS 1034 (CE 977) from Suhāniyā suggests that the ruler was living at that date with full power with the title of *mahārājādhirāja*. From the Rakhetrā rock inscription of Vijayapāladeva, dated VS 999-1000 (CE 942-43), it is confirmed that the region was held by the Pratihāra ruler till at least 942-43 CE.²⁵ Further it is evident that the Pratihāras must have lost it sometime between 942-43 and 977 CE, which is the year of Vajradāmana inscription from Suhāniyā. In the Khajurāho stone inscription of Yaśovarman,²⁶ it is documented that the fort of Gwalior was held by Dhaṅga as early as VS 1011 (CE 953-54). On the assumption that Vajradāmana had captured Gwalior on or before 977 CE, it is observed by most of the scholars that the possible conclusion is that the conquest of Gwalior by the Kacchapaghātas and the Candellas refers to one and the same incident when they sided with each other in defeating the Pratihāra ruler who has been identified as Vijayapāla. We have no record of Vajradāmana after CE 977, so it may be presumed that the reign of the ruler closed after sometime, when he was succeeded by his son, Maṅgalarāja, who is only conventionally described as scattering his enemies as the Sun does the darkness. It is possible that he ruled for a smaller period, after CE 977 and before CE 985. Maṅgalarāja's successor was his son, Kirttirāja who had 'conquered in battle the countless hosts of the prince of Mālava'. The Mālava ruler was identified by scholars as the Paramāra Bhojadeva and they surmise that 'it was practically impossible for a minor chief like Kirttirāja to inflict this terrible shock on the invading forces without the moral and material assistance of his mighty sovereign, the Candella Vidyādhara'²⁷. But in the light of the new date for the accession of Kirttirāja in c. 985 CE there is a possibility that the Mālava ruler conquered in battle by Kirttirāja may be Paramāra Sindhurāja (c. 995-1000 CE). Moreover, in the present scenario there is little evidence to accept the view that 'it is probably Kirttirāja who surrendered to Mahmūd of Ghazni, when the latter invaded

Gwalior in 1021 CE²⁸. That Kacchapaghāta ruler may be a successor of Kirttirāja.

In the light of the Gwalior museum inscription of VS 1038 (CE 981) the antiquity of the Kacchapaghāta family would carry back even beyond Lakṣmaṇa²⁹. Gugga is stated to have served as minister (*san-mantrin*) to the rulers of the Kacchapa dynasty '*bhūpaiḥ Kacchapa-varṇśajaiḥ*', which is the earliest mention of the family name Kacchapa-varṇśa or the Kacchapaghāta dynasty and this expression implies that Gugga was the contemporary and minister of more than two Kacchapa kings. Since the known date of Vacchila, as given in this inscription falls in 981 CE, his great grandfather Gugga, who, according to this inscription was a minister of the Kacchapa rulers, may be considered to have lived towards the end of the 9th century CE. The claim made for Gugga in this inscription is also supported by architectural remains lying loose in the village Suhāniyā or preserved in the Museums. An important ruin at Suhāniyā located in the middle of the village shows that the town was established well before it ascended to importance in the eleventh century under the name Sirhapaniā. The outer wall of the hall and a few stray fragments are all that remain of the early ninth century structure³⁰. Pottery sherds from the large mounds around the present village date from the ninth to fourteenth centuries.

Notes and References

1. F. Kielhorn, "The Sāsahū Temple Inscription of Mahipāla, of Vikrama-Saṁvat 1150", *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XV (1886), p. 36, v.6.
2. *Ibid*, v. 5.
3. 'Saṁvataḥ /1034 Śri Vajradāma mahārājādhirāja Vaisākha vadi pācami.' Rajendralal Mitra, "Vestiges of the Kings of Gwalior", *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*, XXXI (1862), p. 411 and number 6 (Pl. I); D. R. Bhandarkar, "A List of the Inscriptions of Northern India in Brahmi and its derivative Scripts, from about 200 AC". *Appendix to Epigraphia Indica*, vol. XIX to XXIII, no. 86; Alexander Cunningham, *Archaeological Survey of India Reports*, Vol. II (1862-65), Indological Book House, Varanasi, 1972, p. 401; *Annual Administration Report of the Archaeology Department, Gwalior State (GAR)*, no. 20; Michael D. Willis, *Inscriptions of Gopaksetra (IG)*, London, 1996, p. 3.
4. F. Kielhorn, *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XV, p. 36, v. 9.
5. *Ibid*, v. 10.
6. D. R. Patil, *The Cultural Heritage of Madhya Bharat*, Gwalior, 1952, p. 84-85; A. M. Sinha, *Madhya Pradesh District Gazetteers, Morena*, Bhopal, 1996, p. 368.

7. F. Kielhorn, *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XV, p. 36, v. 11.
8. For architectural detail please see, Krishna Deva, *Temples of India*, Aryan Books International, New Delhi, 1995, pp. 176-77; Michael D. Willis, "Architecture in Central India under the Kachhapaghata Rulers", *South Asian Studies*, 12, 1996, pp. 13-32; M. A. Dhaky (ed.), *Encyclopaedia of Indian Temple Architecture: North India Beginning of Medieval Idiom*, AIS, Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts, 1998, pp. 15-34.
9. Ramanath Misra, *Bharatiya Murti Kala ka Itihas*, Granth Silpi, Delhi, 2002, p. 287.
10. S. K. Dixit, *A Guide to the Central Archaeological Museum*, Gwalior, 1962, pp. 44-58.
11. *GAR*, 1983 (1926-27), p.7, pl. III-b.
12. For detail please see, *GAR*, 1982 (1925-26), p. 6-7; *GAR*, 1983 (1926-27), p.7.
13. *Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy (ARIE)* (1961-62), no. C 1587; Willis, *IG*, p. 27: refers that an inscription of VS 1[4]50 is engraved while there are two inscriptions and the date is VS 1950.
14. *JASB*, XXXI (1862): number 17 (Pl. III); *ARIE* (1961-62), no. C 1590; Willis, *IG*, p. 120: read *Śrī Paliyaṣa Purahitaḥ*.
15. *JASB*, XXXI (1862): 422 and number 17 (Pl. III); *ARIE* (1961-62), no. C 1588; Willis, *IG*, p. 30.
16. *ARIE* (1961-62), no. C 1589; Willis, *IG*, p. 120: at the end written *vimalapurasthiti*, in late character.
17. *ARIE* (1961-62), no. C 1591; Willis, *IG*, p. 120: *kaupālā manu*, in the late character.
18. H. C. Ray, *The Dynastic History of Northern India: Early Medieval Period*, Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Delhi, Second edition, 1973, p. 824.
19. *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. VII, Part I, ASI, New Delhi, 1991, p. 124.
20. *GAR*, 1982 (1925-26), p. 6-7.
21. Alexander Cunningham, *Archaeological Survey of India Reports*, Vol. II (1862-65), p. 374.
22. D. R. Patil, *The Cultural Heritage of Madhya Bharat*, p. 84-85.
23. Ramanath Misra, *Bharatiya Murti Kala ka Itihas*, p. 287.
24. *GAR* (VS 1994/AC 1937-38), no. 8; *ARIE* (1961-62), no. C 1478; Willis, *IG*, p. 120.

A. Kakanmaṭha temple of Suhāniyā.

B. Kakanmaṭha temple Inscription of VS 1044.

Kakanmaṭha temple Inscriptions of renovation in VS 1950.

25. GAR (VS 1981/AC 1924-25), no. 32.
26. F. Kielhorn, "Stone Inscription of Yaśovarman, of the year 1011", *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. I (1892), p. 129, v. 45.
27. H. C. Ray, *The Dynastic History of Northern India*, p. 824-825; H. V. Trivedi, *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. VII, Part I, p. 23.
28. D. C. Ganguly 1957. "Northern India During the Eleventh and Twelfth Centuries", in *The Struggle for Empire*, R.C. Majumdar and others (ed.), Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, Bombay, Second edition 1966, Chapter II, p. 56.
29. K.V. Ramesh, and C. L. Suri, "An Unpublished Inscription in the Gwalior Museum Samvat 1038", *Epigraphia Indica*, vol. XL, no. 37, pp. 191-96, p.193.
30. For detail please see, Michael D. Willis, *Temples of Gopakṣetra: A Regional History of Architecture and Sculpture in Central India AD 600-900*, London, 1997, p. 69-70.

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